

ESG KORPORATIV YASHIL RIVOJLANISHNI TARG'IB QILADI

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Energiya taqchilligi kuchayib borayotgan va atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish bo'yicha tobora kuchayib borayotgan ijtimoiy va iqtisodiy rivojlanish sharoitida iqtisodiy manfaatlarga yo'naltirilgan an'anaviy rivojlanish konsepsiyalari va usullari endi bu talabni qondira olmaydi va korxonalarining yashil transformatsiyasiga erishish dolzarbdir. ESGning ilg'or rivojlanish konsepsiyalari va baholash standartlari korxonalarining yashil o'zgarishi va rivojlanishiga yordam berishi mumkin. Iqtisodiy manfaatlar va ekologik muhit o'rtasidagi muvozanatni ta'minlash uchun atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilishni faol ravishda amalga oshiradigan, ijtimoiy mas'uliyatni bajaradigan va ichki tuzilmaviy boshqaruvni kuchaytiradigan rivojlanish modeli korxonalarining yashil va barqaror rivojlanishiga javob berishi mumkin.

Kalit so'zlar: ESG, atrof-muhitni muhofaza qilish, korporativ boshqaruv, ijtimoiy mas'uliyat, yashil rivojlanish.

ESG СОДЕЙСТВУЕТ КОРПОРАТИВНОМУ ЗЕЛЕНОМУ РАЗВИТИЮ

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В сегодняшних условиях социального и экономического развития с растущим дефицитом энергии и все более сильными призывами к защите окружающей среды традиционные концепции и методы развития, ориентированные на экономические выгоды, больше не могут удовлетворить этот спрос, и необходимо срочно добиться «зеленой» трансформации предприятий. Передовые концепции развития и стандарты оценки ESG могут способствовать «зеленой» трансформации и развитию предприятий. Чтобы обеспечить баланс между экономическими выгодами и экологической средой, модель развития, которая активно осуществляет защиту окружающей среды, выполняет социальные обязанности и укрепляет внутреннее структурное управление, может соответствовать зеленому и устойчивому развитию предприятий.

Ключевые слова: ESG, охрана окружающей среды, корпоративное управление, социальная ответственность, зеленое развитие.

ESG PROMOTES CORPORATE GREEN DEVELOPMENT

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In today's social and economic development environment with increasing energy shortages and increasingly strong calls for environmental protection, traditional development concepts and methods focusing on economic benefits can no longer meet this demand, and it is urgent to achieve green transformation of enterprises. ESG's advanced development concepts and evaluation standards can promote the green transformation and development of enterprises. In order to ensure the balance between economic benefits and the ecological environment, a development model that actively carries out environmental protection, fulfills social responsibilities, and

strengthens internal structural governance can meet the green and sustainable development of enterprises.

Keywords: *ESG, environmental protection, corporate governance, social responsibility, green development.*

Climate change has become one of the most severe global challenges in the 21st century. Reducing greenhouse gas emissions and protecting the earth's ecology have become urgent goals. People's attention to climate issues has prompted people to re-examine the production and consumption model. In this process, green economy and green transformation that focus on low-carbon development and environmental protection have become a good way to solve the problem.

Environmental, social and governance (ESG) is a development concept and evaluation standard designed to measure and evaluate the performance of enterprises in environmental, social and governance aspects [1]. In 2004, the United Nations Global Compact released the "Who Cares Who Wins" report and proposed the ESG concept for the first time [2]. Over the past two decades, ESG concepts have been continuously enriched. Today, we believe the areas covered by ESG are:

-In the environment, it involves carbon and greenhouse gas emissions, environmental policy, waste pollution and management policy, energy use and consumption, water use and management policy, biodiversity and water management, and focuses on corporate environmental responsibility and sustainability sex.

-In terms of society, it includes occupational health and safety, employee rights protection, diversity and equal opportunities, labor regulations, product responsibility, labor standards, labor relations, consumer rights protection, employee participation, etc., taking into account the company's responsibility and contribution to society.

-In terms of governance, it involves corporate governance, talent training and gathering, anti-corruption and bribery policies, anti-unfair competition, risk management, tax transparency, fair labor practices, ethical codes of conduct, accounting standards, board composition, etc.

The green and low-carbon concept is highly consistent with the concept of ESG. Vigorously developing ESG will help enterprises to carry out high-quality ESG practices, thereby promoting the green transformation of enterprises and promoting green and sustainable economic and social development.

ESG investing is an investment strategy. ESG originates from responsible investment (PRI). The principles of responsible investment include environmental, social and governance (ESG) factors into the consideration of investment decisions, consider all factors related to investment returns, and take corresponding behavioral measures [3]. The goal of ESG investing is to promote the sustainable development of enterprises and create long-term value for investors by investing in companies that perform well in ESG.

Global ESG investment is showing a rapid development trend. As of March 31, 2023, more than 60 countries around the world, 5,391 institutions have signed to confirm the PRI principles (including 4,841 investors and 550 service providers). The speed of ESG development in Europe has attracted global attention, and the number of signatories in Europe is far ahead of other regions.

Figure 1: Number of UN PRI signatories

Source: [4]

According to Custom Market Insights (CMI), the ESG investment market size is estimated to be US\$17.2 trillion in 2022 and is expected to reach approximately US\$46.5 trillion by 2032. The ESG investment market has very huge development potential.

ESG's promotion of corporate green development is achieved from many aspects due to the nature of ESG itself:

- The ESG concept is in line with the green transformation goals of traditional industries to save energy, reduce emissions, improve quality, and increase efficiency. In order to meet the expectations of ESG investors, companies may increase investments in green technologies and sustainable solutions, thereby driving innovation in products and services and transforming business models. ESG-related short-term incentive policies and long-term market mechanisms can effectively alleviate the difficulties and challenges that companies may encounter in the process of transitioning to green [5].

- ESG investment strategies can help significantly reduce investment risks in key areas such as industry, energy and environmental protection through policy guidance and actual market operations. This investment method can attract more capital to adopt ESG principles and promote the formation of green supply chains. At the same time, it also promotes green technology innovation cooperation between the upstream and downstream of the industrial chain, gradually forming a positive incentive mechanism and a good circulation system.

- ESG can motivate companies to improve their external effects in the economic, social and environmental fields by implementing ESG strategies by optimizing resource allocation and promoting capital flows. This approach encourages companies to increase investment in green technology innovation and promote product upgrades in a more environmentally friendly direction. Through these efforts, the development of low-carbon or zero-carbon green technologies can be promoted, thereby gaining recognition from the international market, government support, favor from investors, and positive evaluations from third-party institutions, thus enhancing its core competitiveness.

Suggestions for corporate green development based on ESG concepts:

1. Environmental protection

Strengthen corporate social responsibility and strengthen ecological and environmental protection and restoration work. Enterprises actively fulfill their corporate social responsibilities and promote environmental protection. In the process of development, enterprises should pay attention to coordinated development with the ecological environment. While developing, we should actively protect the ecological environment, respect nature and ecology, and minimize damage to the ecological environment. Use clean energy to promote energy conservation and emission reduction. Reduce dependence on traditional energy, reduce energy consumption and emissions, and improve energy utilization efficiency.

2. Social management aspects

The government formulates reasonable policies and gives full play to the market value mechanism. The government should fully coordinate social relations and social resources, maintain market stability, and avoid the occurrence of systemic risks. Enterprises should pay attention to the dynamic changes in the consumer market and formulate reasonable price adjustment strategies; develop diversified cooperation to cope with the changing market environment. While pursuing economic interests, enterprises must also assume corresponding social responsibilities. The development of enterprises should focus on long-term social benefits.

3. Internal development of the enterprise

Strengthen self-management and cultivate skilled talents. During the production process, existing technologies and equipment should be continuously improved and promoted, the invention and use of high-tech clean technologies should be encouraged, and technical production should be green, in-depth and large-scale. Enterprises must strengthen the governance of their own internal corporate structures, clarify the division of labor within the enterprise, achieve real-time coordination of various departments, and improve production efficiency. The development of enterprises needs to pay full attention to social benefits, strengthen the responsible management of the supply chain, and comply with relevant laws and regulations.

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